

BuildingSmart Use-Case Definition – EMBODIED CARBON FOOTPRINT ANALYSIS

Section 1: MetaData

1.1 Identification of the document

Title

EMBODIED CARBON FOOTPRINT ANALYSIS – BRICS TOOL

ASHVIN: Assistants for Healthy, Safe and Productive Virtual Construction Design, Operation & Maintenance using a Digital Twin.

Short Text:

Building and organizing a knowledgebase of embodied carbon footprint data by feeding the database from past construction projects and monitoring running construction projects.

Project Status:

Finished

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Introduction:

This document provides background and describes a use case of scoring performance indicator values related to carbon footprint calculation. This document focuses on feedback a database with the embodied carbon footprint data from past and running construction projects. These data allow assessment of the performance of a structure, help to understand the sensitivity of the performance indicators with respect to design changes and support an objective data-based decision-making process in the early design phase.

1.2 Imprint:

Partners:

Paul Merz (Technische Universität Berlin), Timo Hartmann (Technische Universität Berlin)

Section 2: Use-Case Definition

2.1 Data Sheets & Standards

2.2 General Definition of the Use-Case

USE CASE DESCRIPTION	
Title	Embodied Carbon Footprint Analysis
Goal	Building and organizing a knowledgebase of past footbridge projects by constantly scoring performance indicators (PIs) for the carbon footprint data.
Description	Embodied carbon footprint data is computed with ongoing iterations from a finite element model of a construction.
Input Data	Background data - knowledgebase (digital twin data) of past projects that is large enough to be analyzed input data - the development of Finite Element Models

Sequence of actions	1. Enter Input 2. Analyze Output
Primary actors	Designers, Civil Engineers, Design Companies
Secondary actors	Architects
Pre-conditions	Adequate amount of data of the site to generate designs
Trigger	Development of data based scenarios for optimal construction designs
Post-conditions	
Frequency of use	Every project
Support planned for	ASHVIN
UC Created by	
Date of last update	

Figure 1 Use Case Description

Aim and Scope:

The proposed use case aims to present the end-user with a well-structured knowledgebase of digital twin data from past construction projects and monitoring running construction projects. The goal is to create a system which constantly allows for the enrichment of the database, so digital twin data from the construction sites can be used in the early design phase of construction projects.

Objectives:

This document provides an explanation for feeding the database with past and current construction sites data. Performance indicators are calculated to measure the current construction site. Three distinct approaches of Performance Indicator computation, evidence-based design, and generative design interact with each other. Moreover, the steps of design and development of a database with the embodied carbon footprint data are shown in this document. The digital knowledgebase of past footbridge projects is analysed by scoring performance indicators (PIs) for the carbon footprint and efficiency. To track the development of an ongoing footbridge design project PIs are continuously scored and compared during the workflow. Steps towards an improved database scheme can be presented along with the investigation of data storage requirements. The overall process shows the applicability of the

approach even though the available database has major flaws which motivates the introduction of a digital twin as a standardized way of collecting data for future construction projects.

There is a software for structural engineering named Sofistik. From these models of the bridge projects, carbon footprint calculation can be done. This can be seen as carbon footprint calculation the main component for scoring PI values. Direct export of the computed Performance Indicator values into the knowledge database is done. Designers, civil engineers, and design companies are the primary actors for this document. For the activities in this document, the database of sbp (schlaich bergemann partner) company was used.

The Development of Database:

Geometric dimensions

For the geometric dimensions an issue in the sbp database is the inconsistency between the length, the width, and the deck area variable. These three variables should be reduced to two variables as the deck area can be computed by multiplying the length with the width.

Additionally, the length variable might be dropped as the length should be computable from the sum of the spans.

Another topic regarding the geometric dimensions would be bridge type specific dimensions. The sbp database currently contains variables like the pylon height which is only applicable for certain bridge types like cable-span bridges or suspension bridges. One solution could be the introduction of generic dimensions in the general database which would be translated to bridge type specific dimensions using a separate data file as shown in Figure 2.

bridge type	dimension 1	dimension 2	dimension 3
arch	Arch rise	Number of hangers	Arch cross section area
suspension	Pylon height	Cable sag	Pylon cross section area
cable-stayed	Pylon height	Number of cables	Pylon cross section area

Figure 2 Example for the connection of bridge typologies and type specific dimensions

Inclusion of prefabrication related data in the database

To quantify the influence of prefabrication on the PIs of footbridge design the prefabrication status of newly built footbridge design projects should be included in the database. Different approaches for assessing the prefabrication status are available mainly in the building construction sector. An adoption for footbridge design might be useful in this area.

Data Storage requirements

Database storage requirements accompanied by financial and energy related cost might be a major drawback to the implementation of DT for the early design stages. Therefore storage requirements for the currently available data were investigated along with projections for a greatly increasing database of footbridge projects.

The digital twin platform is currently running two different clusters which are shown Figure 3.

Cluster	Specification	Cost
Digital Ocean Cluster x3 nodes	6vCPUs, 12Gb RAM, 240 Gb Disk	24 \$/month
AWS EC2 x3 nodes + RDS: t3.xlarge	4 CPUs, 16.0Gb RAM + db.t2.micro - 2vCPUs, 1Gb RAM, Disk on demand (100Gb scalable to 1000Gb)	420\$ + 750\$ for RDS / month

Figure 3 Currently used clusters with specification and monthly cost.

The footbridge database provided by sbp including around 300 footbridge projects with ca. 70 parameters has a size of 300 kB. For comparison the US National Bridge Inventory database (Administration, 2022) holding over 700,000 us bridges and 123 variables has a size of under 300 MB.

Regarding the power consumption an estimate was made based on (Intel, 2009) a value of between 0.001Kwh and 1Kwh per month was derived for a potential database size of 300 MB. This translates to the emission of between 0,042 gCO₂eq and 420 gCO₂eq in case of energy production in Germany (Umweltbundesamt, 2022).

It can be concluded that the cost and energy related ramifications of the storage of digital twin data for the design phase of footbridge projects is very small and therefore doesn't pose a major obstacle in the implementation of the approach.

Sensor-based data within the design workflow

The data presented in this report is based on geometric dimensions or site-specific conditions as well as PI values which are the result of computations or observations during or after the construction. This data is not sensor-based but originates from 3D-models, site investigations or design/construction computations.

This section explores the possibilities to interact with this topic in the design phase.

Design insights for sensor placement

One important aspect is the placement of sensor during the construction or maintenance phase of a footbridge. Due to the cost of sensor installation and the large amount of data produced by sensors (especially compared to the database sizes discussed in section 0) the strategic placement of a limited number of sensors requires careful attention.

The designers of the footbridge have insight knowledge of its structural behaviour and are thereby predestined to also plan for possible sensor positions in the design stage of the footbridge. These sensor positions should be stored in the DT during the design stage so that their installation in later stages of the lifespan is informed by the designers' decisions.

If the Evidence Based Design provides safety warnings for the construction of the footbridge the installation of sensors like motion trackers might be prompted to the designer as a recommendation. This way sensor installation could be a mean to enhance construction safety.

Using sensor data in the knowledge database

Another aspect of the sensor data is the inclusion of insights made from this historic DT data into the knowledge database.

One possible use case could be the design load estimation. In the example of footbridges, a strain gauge measuring the strain in the lower part of the cross section could be used to calculate the real loading of the footbridge. Another possibility would be camera images capturing the real occupancy of the footbridge in discrete time intervals. Collecting this data for several footbridges and including it into the knowledge database would enable engineers to compare the loading required by design codes with the evidence-based prediction. If the real loading is significantly smaller than the design load this could lead to a revision of the design code. Smaller design loads then influence the dimensions of newly built footbridges and would lead to less material being necessary, thereby reducing the PIs of material cost and carbon footprint.

2.3 Overall Process:

The Embodied Carbon Footprint Analysis use case aims to measure the performance of the current construction site and to feedback constantly the database with the embodied carbon footprint data from new projects.

The overall process for this feedback from past projects is presented in Figure 4. The design workflow starts with the choosing and activating the bridge model, which is prepared in structural engineering software (sofistik). The constraints from the design task are fed into the evidence based design knowledge database which contains PIs scores. The generative design use case enables to evaluate options according to PIs to determine pareto-optimal options. The resulting digital twin data can then be assessed using the knowledge database.

The embodied carbon footprint during the construction phase and after the construction phase are calculated. After that step, they can be scored by comparing them to the previous key performance Indicators.

In the end, the actual performance of the construction site can be understood and the database can be updated with the feedback.

Figure 4 Process Map

Implementation on #8 Footbridge in Dortmund, Germany

The City of Dortmund is planning to replace the existing Lindemannstrasse foot and cycle path bridge, which connects Max-Ophüls-Platz with the forecourt of the Dortmund Trade Fair Centre. The bridge crosses the Rheinlanddamm, a highly frequented inner-city main road with six lanes. $51^{\circ}29'52.1''N$ $7^{\circ}27'11.7''E$ are the coordinates of the footbridge location.

The design workflow starts with the creation or receiving of the design task, which includes the project-specific details such as the location of the proposed project include requirements for bridge crossing, for example. The constraints from the design task are fed into the evidence-based design assistant. The Evidence-Based design database is based on a knowledge database of built footbridges, which is used to provide insights into the ongoing design process.

The designer of the new footbridge interacts with the evidence-based design database to identify desirable parameter combinations and bridge typologies, thereby enabling the use of a parametric modelling tool to build a more detailed model of the identified subspace of the design space.

The generative design modeler enables the evaluation of options according to performance indicators and, thus, determines Pareto optimal options, which form the basis for decision-

making. These Pareto optimal solutions are to be assessed by decision-makers to select one possible bridge design to be investigated further during detailed design.

All newly built projects are then designed and constructed using a digital twin. This digital twin data can then be assessed using the BSofistik2CarbonFootprint tool which computes performance indicators from the raw digital twin data. The knowledge database is stored on the Evaluation and recommendations for an evidence-based design for productivity, resource efficiency, and safety based on historical digital twin data.

The Sofistik2CarbonFootprint tool closes the loop with the knowledge database thereby creating a system that constantly allows for the enrichment of the knowledge database with every newly constructed footbridge.

Structural analysis can be performed using 3D Finite Element Models (FEM) which can be implemented e.g. using the structural analysis software Sofistik. A 3D-representation of the model is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5 Sofistik FE-Model of the footbridge of demo #8

This tool provides the functionality to directly compute a carbon footprint of the embodied carbon of the structure from a Sofistik Finite Element model. Figure 6 shows a screenshot of the tool with the input of the bridge database and project number on the left side and the textual representation of the computed carbon footprint on the right.

Figure 6 Screenshot of the information tab of the Sofistik2CarbonFootprint Tool

Other graphical representations of the computed carbon footprint are also available in the tool as shown in Figure 7 and Figure 8.

The By Group tab of the tool presents a bar chart of the carbon footprint divided into the different material types and structural elements. The history chart gives insights into the development of the model's carbon footprint when several model iterations are provided.

Figure 7 Distribution of the embodied carbon across structural components

Figure 8 Development of the carbon footprint of different Finite Element models of demo #8

Implementation on #11 Footbridge in Rathenow, Germany

Demonstration site #11 is a completed footbridge in the city of Rathenow, Germany. The footbridge consists of two arches and spans across the Havel River in a curved shape. Within the rages of the arches, the bridge deck widens to allow for seating spaces. The input Finte Element model of the footbridge is shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Sofistik FE-Model of the footbridge of demo #11

This bridge was subject to inhouse carbon footprint computations within project partner company sbp and this allowed for benchmarking of the tools output with the human conducted calculations. The global warming potential for the structure alone according to sbp calculations is computed as 2290.575 t, which is slightly more than the computation of the Sofistik2CarbonFootprint tool with 2155.2 t (see Figure 10). This difference could be connected to the fact that the Sofistik2CarbonFootprint does not compute concrete reinforcements.

project_ID:	Deck Area:
2965	1110 [m ²]
carbon footprint:	footprint per area:
2155.2 [t CO ₂ e]	1.9 [t CO ₂ e/m ²]

Figure 10: Output values for demo site #11

2.4 Disciplines:

*Design discipline- Architecture, Engineering, Design Support;
Project Management discipline- cost estimation, proposal preparation, and scheduling*

2.5 Life Cycle Stages:

Outline conceptual design and full conceptual design.

Section 3: Process-definition

Life cycle stages: Outline conceptual design and full conceptual design

Section 4: Exchange Requirements

In Figure 6, exchange requirements among tools are shown. Firstly, with the preparation of the data file, the user gives input to the database. From the database, real time and past construction site data are sent. After the configuration process, this data is sent to discrete event simulation and, a data file is created for the visualization which will be shown by the visualisation software.

Figure 6 Exchange Requirements

Section 5: Change Log

This is a section only for changes made after publishing to the front end